

Local Structure and Spectroscopic Studies of Mn^{2+} Infused Single Crystals of $Cd(NH_4)_2(SO_4)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$

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ABSTRACT

The parameters of zero field splitting of the Mn^{2+} infused $Cd(NH_4)_2(SO_4)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ (CAS) single crystals are calculated utilizing the superposition model. The evaluated parameters match well with those determined from EPR. The inference of experiment that the Cd^{2+} site is replaced by the Mn^{2+} ion in CAS is verified by theoretical study. The crystal's optical spectra are computed with the help of crystal field parameters obtained from the superposition model and crystal field analysis program. A fair matching is obtained with the experimental band positions. Hence, the experimental observations are confirmed by the theoretical computations.

Keywords: Inorganic compounds, Electron paramagnetic resonance, Zero field splitting, Single crystal, Crystal fields, Superposition model.

1. INTRODUCTION

EPR and electronic absorption techniques have been used effectively to estimate the site symmetry and behaviour of the Mn^{2+} ion in different lattices [1-2]. Many studies have been reported on Mn^{2+} impurities introduced into diamagnetic lattices at room temperature due to its zero field splitting sensitivity to small structural changes [3-5].

The superposition model (SPM) is normally used to model the crystal field (CF) and zero field splitting (ZFS) parameters for application in various other studies [6–10]. SPM and the point-charge model [11, 12, 13] are mostly used to find the parameters of the crystal field (CF). SPM was proposed for CF under certain assumptions [14]. Finding a static spherical polar coordinate system (R_L , θ_L , Φ_L) for each ion or ligand from the host crystal's X-ray structural data is important for carrying out an SPM analysis on the CF. Inter-ionic bonding, ionic size and ionic charge mismatches are likely to give rise some local distortion when transition metal ions are infused. Critical analysis of experimental spin-Hamiltonian parameters for Mn^{2+} and Fe^{3+} in CaO and MgO crystals has been done [15] providing the SPM parameters and showing that the CF for 3d ions satisfies the superposition principle. SPM intrinsic parameters based on reliable ligand distances have been determined for the alkali earth oxides, [16].

The general formula $A_2^+ B^{2+} (XO_4)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ crystals are known as Tutton single crystals where A is a monovalent cation, B is a divalent cation (usually a transition metal ion) and X is sulfur or selenium [17–18]. Tutton crystals are famous isostructural crystal family with the same monoclinic symmetry, the space group $P2_1/a$ and two formula units per unit cell $Z = 2$ [19]. The Tutton crystals (salts) are important crystals because they are used enormously in UV filters [20].

Cadmium ammonium sulfate hexahydrate crystals (CAS) are crystallized in the monoclinic crystal system and belong to the Tutton crystalline salts. Because of their suitable crystal sizes, high purity and small transparency in the UV region, they could be the potential candidates for optoelectronic applications [21]. Cadmium sulfate ($CdSO_4$) has various uses, including electroplating, pigment production, and as a component in batteries and solar cells [22]. Ammonium sulfate is widely used as a fertilizer for alkaline soils. It has a role as a NMR chemical shift reference compound [23]. Cadmium ammonium sulfate is likely related to the individual uses of its constituent compounds.

EPR study of Mn^{2+} infused CAS has been done at 298 K and the spin-Hamiltonian parameters have been estimated [24]. From angular variation studies, it is concluded that magnetic $[Mn(H_2O)_6]^{2+}$ complexes are created when the Mn^{2+} ion enters the divalent sites of the Tutton salt lattice. The a^*bc axis system, where a^* is perpendicular to b and c , (crystal axes) is used to discuss the orientations. The angular variation of the spectrum showed that the crystal field symmetry is orthorhombic.

In the present work, the ZFS parameters D and E are estimated for the Mn^{2+} ion in CAS at 298 K (room temperature, RT) taking CF parameters from SPM and perturbation equations [25]. The aim is to locate the Mn^{2+} ion and the distortion taking place in the CAS crystal. The results for the Mn^{2+} ion at the substitutional Cd^{2+} site in CAS crystal with local distortion yield good agreement with the EPR experimental values. Further goal of the study is to find the extent to which CF theory and SPM technique can be applied to Mn^{2+} ions in CAS crystals in order to produce an SPM parameter database. This will find molecular nanomagnet (MNM) design and computer simulation of their magnetic and spectroscopic properties. The transition ion-based MNM class currently includes single-molecule magnets (SMM) [26], single-chain magnets (SCM) [27], and single ion magnets (SIM) [28]. Due to interesting magnetic properties of MNM,

such as magnetization's macroscopic quantum tunneling and possible uses in high-density information storage and quantum computing, the above systems have attracted an enormous attention from scientists and researchers [26, 27]. There are various synthesized SCM or SMM systems with Mn^{2+} and Cr^{3+} ions [29]. Because of the fact that model calculations for simpler crystal systems can be used as a basis for more complex ones, the parameters of the model found in this case may be used for ZFS parameter computations for Mn^{2+} ions at appropriate sites in MNM. This work's modeling can be extended to obtain various crystals of scientific and industrial importance in a number of other ion-host systems.

2. CRYSTAL STRUCTURE

The crystal structure of Tutton salt CAS is monoclinic with space group $P 2_1/a$ [30]. The unit cell's parameters are as follows: $Z = 2$, $\beta = 106.86^\circ$, $a = 9.433$, $b = 12.823$ and $c = 6.286$ Å. All other divalent cations in the unit cell are in general positions, with the two inequivalent ones located at points $(0, 0, 0)$ and $(1/2, 1/2, 0)$. Water molecules form a slightly warped octahedron around each divalent cation. The other Tutton salts exhibit the same pattern of bond length, with the Cd-O(9) bond being shorter than the Cd-O(8) and Cd-O(7) bonds. Figure 1 shows the symmetry adopted axis system (SAAS) and CAS crystal structure.

Fig. 1. The room-temperature CAS crystal structure and the symmetry-adopted axis system (SAAS).

3. CRYSTAL FIELD AND ZERO FIELD SPLITTING PARAMETER CALCULATIONS

The EPR spectra can be analyzed with the spin Hamiltonian [7]:

$$E(S_x^2 - S_y^2) + D \left\{ S_z^2 - \frac{1}{3} S(S+1) \right\} + \mu_B B.g.S = \mathcal{H} \quad (1)$$

where B, μ_B , g, D and E are the applied magnetic field, Bohr magneton, splitting factor, second rank axial, and second rank rhombic ZFS parameters [31–32]. The a^* , b and c modified crystallographic axes (a^* is normal to axes b and c) and the laboratory x, y, z axes are shown in Fig. 1. The directions of metal-ligand bonds being mutually perpendicular are referred to as the symmetry adopted axes (SAA) or the local symmetry axes of the site. As shown in Fig.1, z axis-Z of SAAS is along the crystal axis- c, and (X, Y) are perpendicular to the axis-Z. When Mn^{2+} ions are infused in CAS crystal, they occupy Cd^{2+} (1) sites with some local distortion in the lattice [33].

The Mn^{2+} ion spin Hamiltonian is given as [34],

$$\mathcal{H}_o + \mathcal{H}_{so} + \mathcal{H}_{ss} + \mathcal{H}_c = \mathcal{H} \quad (2)$$

$$\mathcal{H}_c = \sum B_{kq} C_q^{(k)} \quad (3)$$

where B_{kq} , in Wybourne notation, represent the CF parameters and $C_q^{(k)}$, the spherical tensor operators. $B_{kq} \neq 0$ in the orthorhombic symmetry crystal field only for $k = 2, 4$; $q = 0, 2, 4$. Using SPM, the CF parameters B_{kq} in CAS are computed [34].

The symmetry of the local field about Mn^{2+} ions in CAS crystal is orthorhombic (OR-type I) [7], where the ZFS parameters D and E are estimated as follows [35]:

$$D = \left(\frac{3\zeta^2}{70P^2D'} \right) [-B_{20}^2 - 21\zeta B_{20} + 2B_{22}^2] + \left(\frac{\zeta^2}{63P^2G} \right) [-5B_{40}^2 - 4B_{42}^2 + 14B_{44}^2] \quad (4)$$

$$E = \left(\frac{\sqrt{6}\zeta^2}{70P^2D'} \right) [2B_{20} - 21\zeta] B_{22} + \left(\frac{\zeta^2}{63P^2G} \right) [3\sqrt{10}B_{40} + 2\sqrt{7}B_{44}] B_{42} \quad (5)$$

Here $D' = 17B + 5C$, $P = 7B + 7C$, $G = 10B + 5C$. B and C represent Racah parameters and ζ , the spin-orbit coupling parameter. Utilizing average covalency parameter N, $B = N^4 B_0$, $C = N^4 C_0$, $\zeta = N^2 \zeta_0$, where ζ_0 gives free ion spin-orbit coupling parameter and B_0 and C_0 are Racah parameters for free ion [34, 36]. $\zeta_0 = 336 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $B_0 = 960 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $C_0 = 3325 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ for free Mn^{2+} ion [7].

The covalency parameter N is estimated from $N = (\sqrt{B/B_0} + \sqrt{C/C_0})/2$ using Racah parameters ($B = 835 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $C = 3016 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) obtained from optical study of Mn^{2+} ion in CAS [37].

The CF parameters using SPM are computed [14, 35], with co-ordination factor $K_{kq}(\theta_j, \phi_j)$ and intrinsic parameter $\bar{A}_k(R_j)$, as

$$B_{kq} = \sum_j K_{kq}(\theta_j, \phi_j) \bar{A}_k(R_j) \quad (6)$$

$\overline{A}_k(R_j)$ is found from

$$\overline{A}_k(R_0) \left(\frac{R_0}{R_j} \right)^{t_k} = \overline{A}_k(R_j) \quad (7)$$

where the ligand's distance from the d^n ion is denoted by R_j , $\overline{A}_k(R_0)$ is the intrinsic parameter, R_0 is the reference distance of the ligand from the metal ion and t_k gives power law exponent. For Mn^{2+} infused crystals, $t_2 = 3$ and $t_4 = 7$ [35]. Since the co-ordination about Mn^{2+} ion is octahedral, \overline{A}_4 is computed from the relation [38]

$$\overline{A}_4(R_0) = \frac{3}{4} Dq \quad (8)$$

From optical study [37], $Dq = 690 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Therefore, $\overline{A}_4(R_0) = 517.5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. For $3d^5$ ions the ratio $\frac{\overline{A}_2}{\overline{A}_4}$ falls in the range 8 - 12 [34, 39-40]. With $\overline{A}_2 = 10 \overline{A}_4$, $\overline{A}_2 = 5175 \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Using the ligand configuration around Mn^{2+} ion displayed in Fig. 1 and SPM, the CF parameters of the Mn^{2+} ion at the $Cd^{2+}(1)$ sites are evaluated. Table 1 gives atoms' coordinates in CAS single crystal with bond length R (with and without distortion) and angles θ , ϕ for site I. The ZFS and CF parameters as well as R_0 , reference distance are given in Table 2. Table 2 shows that $R_0 = 0.200 \text{ nm}$ being slightly less than the sum of radii of ions (0.223 nm) of $Mn^{2+} = 0.083 \text{ nm}$ and $O^{2-} = 0.140 \text{ nm}$ with no distortion yield ZFS parameter values at octahedral substitutional site I to be different from the EPR experimental ones [24]. Experimental parameters of ZFS $|D|$ and $|E|$ (10^{-4} cm^{-1}) for site I from EPR are 250.0, 50.0, respectively. $|E|/|D|$ is obtained as 0.200 being smaller than the standard value 0.33 [32]. $|D|$ and $|E|$ estimated theoretically without distortion are larger than the EPR experimental values. The value of $|E|/|D|$ is also larger than the standard value 0.33 [32]. Hence, local distortion is introduced into calculation. Using above value of R_0 and local distortion, the ZFS parameter values for substitutional octahedral sites I are in good match with the EPR experimental ones [24]. The parameters $t_2 = 3$ and $t_4 = 7$ with transformation S2 for standardization [32] are used to get $|E|/|D|$ ratio near to 0.33 and calculated ZFS parameters very close to experimental values from EPR.

Table 1. Atoms' coordinates, bond length R (with and without distortion) and angles θ , ϕ in CAS single crystal (site I).

Mn ²⁺ Position	Ligands	Spherical polar co-ordinates of ligands								
		x	y	z	R(nm)	θ°	ϕ°			
Without distortion										
Site : Substitutional Cd(1) (0.0000, 0.0000, 0.0000)	O7	0.1839	0.1149	0.1745	0.22977	R ₁	85.64	θ_1	85.40	ϕ_1
	O8	-0.1730	0.1200	0.0336	0.22968	R ₂	89.16	θ_2	94.32	ϕ_2
	O9	0.0001	-0.0760	0.3210	0.22405	R ₃	81.76	θ_3	90.00	ϕ_3
	O7'	-0.1839	-0.1149	-0.1745	0.22977	R ₄	94.35	θ_4	94.60	ϕ_4
	O8'	-0.1839	0.3851	0.6745	0.70454	R ₅	84.51	θ_5	91.50	ϕ_5
	O9'	0.1839	0.6149	0.3255	0.82041	R ₆	87.73	θ_6	88.71	ϕ_6
With distortion										
I	O1				0.29977		67.64		86.90	
	O2				0.29348		71.16		92.32	
	O3				0.29406		62.76		88.00	
	O4				0.30677		85.35		90.60	
	O5				0.78954		82.51		91.50	
	O6				0.90541		89.73		90.71	

Table 2. The Mn²⁺ doped CAS crystal's CF and ZFS parameters.

Site	R ₀ (nm)	Parameters of CF (cm ⁻¹)					Parameters of ZFS (10 ⁻⁴ cm ⁻¹)		
		B ₂₀	B ₂₂	B ₄₀	B ₄₂	B ₄₄	D	E	E / D
Without distortion									
Site I $\frac{\overline{A_2}}{\overline{A_4}}=10$	0.200	-13766.2	-16990.6	2257.258	2400.222	4498.851	1999.6	1036.2	0.518
With distortion									
Site I $\frac{\overline{A_2}}{\overline{A_4}}=10$	0.200	-5510.88	2775.973	2.52748	63.37507	2429.446	250.0	82.2	0.329
						Exp.	250.0	50.0	0.200

The CFA computer program [41] and B_{kq} parameters (with distortion) are used to calculate the optical spectra of Mn^{2+} infused CAS single crystals. By diagonalizing the full Hamiltonian, the energy band positions of Mn^{2+} ion are calculated.

Table 3 gives the energy band positions (experimental and calculated) for substitutional site I [37].

Table 3. Both calculated and experimental Energy bands of single crystal of CAS doped Mn^{2+} .

Transition from ${}^6A_{1g}(S)$ state	Experimental band (cm^{-1})	Calculated band (cm^{-1}) I
${}^4T_{1g}(G)$	19380	23820, 23827, 24028, 24085, 24250, 24311
${}^4T_{2g}(G)$	23668	24399, 24411, 24583, 24619, 24659, 24699
${}^4A_{1g}(G)$	24844	24913, 24942
${}^4E_g(G)$	24922	24946, 24954, 24963, 24975
${}^4T_{2g}(D)$	27972	25884, 26906, 26964, 27288, 27364, 28865
${}^4E_g(D)$	29762	29255, 29298, 29712, 29798
${}^4T_{1g}(P)$	31948	30176, 30254, 31075, 31110, 35552, 35599

${}^4A_{2g}(F)$	38760	38083, 38977
${}^4T_{1g}(F)$		40650, 40697, 40715, 40763, 40821, 40887

It is found from Table 3 that the calculated and experimental energy band positions agree reasonably well. Therefore, the theoretical results verify the EPR experimental one [24, 37] that Mn^{2+} ions enter the CAS crystal at substitutional $Cd^{2+}(1)$ octahedral site. The model parameters obtained may be utilized in ZFS parameter evaluations for Mn^{2+} ions at similar molecular nano magnet sites.

5. CONCLUSIONS

To determine the splitting parameters of zero field, the superposition model and perturbation theory are applied for CAS single crystals infused with Mn^{2+} ions. The determined ZFS parameters match well with the experimental values from EPR. The calculated positions of the optical energy bands match reasonably well with those from the experiment. Thus, the theoretical analysis verifies the experimental result that Mn^{2+} ions substitute at $Cd^{2+}(1)$ sites in CAS. The model parameters evaluated in this study may be utilized for ZFS parameter determinations for Mn^{2+} ions at appropriate sites in MNM. The above modeling technique may be useful in yielding different crystals of various scientific and industrial applications.

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Declarations

Ethical Approval: There were no human or animal subjects in this study, and it wasn't conducted in any protected or private locations. Corresponding locations did not require any special permissions.

Competing interests: The authors affirm that no known conflicting financial interests or personal relationships could have influenced any of the work presented in this paper.

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Ram Kripal: concept and oversight.

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